

ACCIDENT DETECTION AND SMART RESCUE SYSTEM USING ANDROID SMARTPHONE WITH MICROPHONE SENSOR OF REAL TIME GPS LOCATION

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Abstract:

The current situation of national issues is vehicle accidents. We can discuss how to communicate with the accident victim immediately. We can use microphone sensors with frequency of vibration and Global Positioning System location with tracking victim location spontaneously. It accesses any platform like android, ios, and linux. An accident was done, our sensor was detected and played the sound of the alarm. if the victim cannot stop the alarm; it spontaneously sends the location and information for nearby hospitals.

Keywords: GPS Locator, Microphone sensor, Automation services.